

LOGIN

Today, the formation of students' written speech competencies in the educational process is considered one of the urgent tasks. Written speech plays an important role in developing students' communicative culture, thinking, and creative abilities. Therefore, the issue of improving the methodological training of future primary school teachers requires scientific research. The harmonious use of various pedagogical approaches in the effective organization of this process is a requirement of the time.

The effective organization of the process of improving the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers for the development of students' written and oral competencies is interconnected with the selected approaches, principles and conditions. An approach is a way of looking at teaching and learning. The approach to studying any subject is based on a theoretical view of what the subject is and how it can be studied. An approach creates methods that use classroom activities or methods that help students learn, a way of teaching something. General characteristics of the approach: Goal-oriented - serves to achieve a specific result. Methodological in nature - directs scientific research or practical activities. Adaptability - can be used in different ways depending on different conditions and tasks. Systematicity - helps to study the object as a whole [4].

The integrative approach is described by the scientist R.A. Mavlonova as follows: "Integration" means "whole", so let's consider what this process of thinking is as a phenomenon from a conceptual and methodological point of view, and what integration is from a conceptual and methodological point of view [1]. The integration process (from Latin integration – connection, restoration) is the gathering of previously separate parts and elements of a system into a single whole based on their interdependence and complementarity. By integration in the pedagogical process, researchers understand the aspects of the development process associated with the integration of previously separate parts.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

The integrative approach organizes the process of developing written and spoken competence on a multifaceted and systematic basis. According to this approach, the process of developing written speech activity should not be limited only to the lessons of the subject of native language-reading literacy and its teaching methodology, but should be carried out in close connection with literature, foreign languages, technology and social sciences. Such integration is based on the mutual harmony of linguistics, psycholinguistics, cognitive pedagogy and communicative methodology, and will deeply develop the speech activity and written expression skills of future teachers [5]. Integration with literature and social sciences gives effective results, since these disciplines implement the process of developing the abilities of future teachers to think critically, analyze the text contextually and understand linguistic semantics.

The use of technologies and interactive teaching methods in the process of developing written speech activity.

In the process of developing students' written and oral competencies, future primary school teachers are given various tasks based on the integration of their native

language and natural sciences. For example: “Child of Nature”, “A Wonderful Creature”, “There is no life without water”, “Wonders of Nature”, “I am a part of nature”. The tasks are to read the texts “Mountains and Deserts”, “Wonders of the World” and draw a picture according to the text.

Competency-based approach is aimed at developing the personality, and the main values help to determine the direction and guide it. The main component of the competency-based approach is the organization of independent educational activities of students. On its basis, the “principle of consciousness and activity, competency-based approach in education” is implemented. The competency-based approach aims to develop a set of knowledge, skills and competencies necessary for the development of written and verbal competence, and its main principle is to ensure that future teachers are oriented to their practical activities and can effectively use written speech in real situations and within the framework of various topics. The competency-based approach is not only focused on providing theoretical knowledge, but also forms solid skills by enriching students' experience of using written expression for specific communicative purposes. Based on this approach, future teachers first acquire knowledge on performing written creative tasks in order to develop written and verbal competences, and then, based on the knowledge they have accumulated, they acquire the skills to form written and verbal competences in students. In particular, future teachers were given tasks on writing a report, essay, and creative story. “The main essence of competency-based teaching is that the knowledge, skills and qualifications acquired by students in the process of education and upbringing, organized in vocational subjects, should be used in their personal lives to solve problems they encounter and to have the necessary basic competencies to be competitive in their profession [2]. An example of exercises based on a competency-based approach could be as follows:

1. Vocabulary expansion exercises

- Make a sentence from the 10 given words.
- Write 5 phrases on the topics of “nature”, “friendship”, “book”.

2. Exercises on sentence and text construction

- Write a short text of 4–5 sentences based on a picture.
- Arrange the given sentences in a logical order and create a story.

3. Creative writing exercises

- Write a short essay on the topic “If I were a pilot...”
- Write a letter to your favorite hero.

4. Analytical exercises

- Write the main idea from a small text.
- Find unnecessary sentences in the text, shorten them and rewrite them.

5. Practical writing exercises

- Write a letter inviting your friend to your birthday.
- Write a formal application to the teacher (about using the school library).

Person-centered approach. “Person-centered education is education that is maximally focused on the development of the individual, his or her own characteristics” [3].

RESULTS

The person-centered approach emphasizes directing the process of developing written and verbal competence towards personal and professional growth. It develops not only skills related to written speech, but also abilities such as self-assessment, setting life goals, and developing personal growth strategies. In addition, it is aimed at developing a person with intellectual abilities, emotional development needs, creative inclinations and development opportunities. The following exercises can be recommended for this: Interest-based Exercises: Ask the student to write a short text about his/her favorite hobby (for example: football, drawing, singing). Write a short essay on the topic "My dream profession". Optional exercises: Three topics are given: "The most beautiful day in nature", "My best friend", "My favorite book". The student chooses the one he/she wants and writes a text. Chooses one of the given pictures and composes a story. Creative exercises: Write a fairy tale on the topic "If I were a magician..." Continue the given sentence and create a story: "This morning, on my way to school, I encountered an amazing event..." Exercises based on personal experience: A short essay on the topic "My most memorable day(s)". Write a diary entry about a family holiday. Free expression exercises: The student expresses his/her thoughts in writing based on a poem or proverb he/she likes. "What makes me happy?" free essay on the topic. Reflective exercises: At the end of the lesson, write a written answer to the question "What did I learn today?". Compose a short text on the topic "If I were a teacher..."

DISCUSSION

Individual approach The training process is aimed at adapting teaching methods and materials to the specific needs of each future primary school teacher, taking into account the level of knowledge and learning styles, and working with various tasks to develop written speech skills. Based on the individual approach, the content of written exercises is modified based on the individual needs, linguistic potential and level of mastery of the student [6]. For example, written tasks are gradually complicated, initially focusing on the correct use of simple grammar and lexical units, and then on the development of analytical and creative writing skills. The advantages of the individual approach are to give separate tasks to future teachers with different levels of mastery (high, medium, low). To complete tasks on topics they like (poetry, essay, thesis, essay). Each student can freely express their opinion. Identify their mistakes, shortcomings, gaps in their knowledge and give them targeted exercises.

For example: We gave three different levels of assignments on the topic "Uzbekistan is my homeland".

High: Write a story with a complex plot.

Medium: Continue the given story.

Low: Compose a simple story based on the picture.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the combination of person-oriented, competency-based, activity-oriented, integrative and innovative approaches is of great importance in improving the methodological training of future primary school teachers. Their use allows for the

effective formation of written and verbal competence in students, encouragement of independent thinking and development of creative abilities.

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